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Board of Directors and Earnings Management: Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group

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Abstract

Purpose - The purpose of this paper is to examine the effectiveness of Board of Directors in reducing earnings management activities in listed non-financial services sector in Nigeria.

Design/Methodology/Approach - Earnings management is seen through discretionary accruals as suggested by Kothari et al. (2005). Board of directors is measured using six characteristics: board size, independence, meetings, CEO duality, audit committee, nomination and remuneration committee. These characteristics are tested using a sample of 75 non-financial services companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The study covers a period of 10 years (2012-2021). The hypotheses are tested using multiple regression analysis.

Findings - The results show that some Board of Directors characteristics, such as size and independence, are negatively associated with earnings management at significant levels. The originality of this research is its extension of the literature on the role of Board of Directors in reducing earnings management activities in Nigeria.

Research Implications - These results provide empirical evidence to assist regulators in identifying effective Board of Directors characteristics. The findings are also useful to shareholders and capital market operators in evaluating the roles of Board of Directors in reducing earnings management activities in Nigeria.

Research Limitations - However, the study is limited to listed non-financial services firms because financial services companies come under strict regulations from the Central Bank of Nigeria, Nigerian Deposit Corporation and Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria.

Key words: Agency Theory, Audit Committee Independence, Board of Directors, Board Independence, Board Meetings, Board Size, CEO Duality, Earnings Management, Nomination and Remuneration Committee

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1. Introduction

Nigeria like the rest of the World, between 2007 and 2008, witnessed financial crisis of large proportion only imagined in the literature. Ever since then, several regulations and reforms have been introduced to avoid similar crisis in the future. Regulators were concerned about earnings management, especially after the collapse of several large firms in the World. Earnings management has been blamed for many of these major collapses as it masks the true financial results and position of businesses and obscures facts that stakeholders ought to know. One of the most useful definitions for earnings management, according to Healy and Wahlen (1999) is that “earnings management occurs when managers use judgment in financial reporting and in structuring transactions to alter financial reports to either mislead some stakeholders about the underlying economic performance of the company or to influence contractual outcomes that depend on reported accounting numbers.”

Earnings management produces less reliable accounting earnings that do not reflect a firm's financial performance. Earnings management is likely to reduce the quality of reported earnings and its usefulness for investment decisions, thus reducing investor confidence in the financial reports. However, accounting earnings are more reliable and of higher quality when managers' opportunistic behaviour is reduced using monitoring systems. One of the fundamental corporate governance structures to restore investors' trust and confidence on the capital market is the Board of Directors. Board of Directors' primary objective is to resolve agency problems by aligning management's interests with the interests of shareholders (Demsetz & Lehn, 1985). The Board of Directors exists to encourage the efficient use of resources and equally to require accountability for the stewardship of those resources. It is widely accepted that board of directors limits a manager's ability to manipulate earnings (Beasley, 1996; Dechow *et al.*, 1996; Peasnell *et al.*, 2000; Chtourou *et al.*, 2001; Xie *et al.*, 2003; Park & Shin, 2004; Peasnell *et al.*, 2005; Jaggi *et al.*, 2009, Lo *et al.*, 2010; Dimitropoulos & Asteriou, 2010). In Nigeria, Samuel (2006) investigated publicly listed firms and found that earnings management behaviour differs according to the industry type. This study is concerned about the effectiveness of the Board of Directors in reducing earnings management among listed non-financial services firms.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Board Independence

Most of the prior studies on the relationship between Board of Directors and earnings management document a negative relationship between the presence of outside directors and the occurrence of fraudulent financial statements or discretionary accounting accruals (Peasnell *et al.*, 2000; Peasnell *et al.*, 2005; Bedard *et al.*, 2004; Klein, 2002b; Xie *et al.*, 2003; Benkel, *et al.*, 2006; Niu, 2006; Osma, 2008; Jaggi *et al.*, 2009, Lo *et al.*, 2010 and Dimitropoulos and Asteriou 2010). In the USA, Xie *et al.* (2003) hypothesise that companies with a larger proportion of independent directors will be less likely to engage in earnings management than those whose boards which have a majority of executive directors. Their results support their hypothesis. Klein (2002b) finds a significant negative association between discretionary accruals and the proportion of independent directors on the board, and whether the board has a majority of independent directors. In the UK, Peasnell *et al.* (2005), find that firms with a higher proportion of outside directors have less income-increasing accruals. Another interesting UK study carried out by Peasnell *et al.* (2000), find that post-Cadbury period indicates less income-increasing accrual management to avoid loss of earnings or earnings decline when the proportion of non-executive directors is high. In Canada, Park and Shin (2004); Niu (2006) and Chang and Sun (2009) demonstrate that the level of independence of board composition is negatively related to the level of abnormal accruals.

A European study by Osma and Nogue (2007) tests whether board composition is effective in constraining earnings manipulation in a sample of Spanish quoted companies during the period 1999-2001 for a sample of 155 firm-year observations. Whereas, in the US, UK and Canada independent directors play a significant role. They find that, in Spain, the key practice to constrain earnings management is the appointment of institutional directors. On the basis of their findings, they conjectured that importing the Anglo-Saxon model of Board of Directors is probably not the best solution for code-law countries, such as Spain. Spanish firms have very different governance structures from their American counterparts, including important family and institutional blockholders that effectively supervise managers. Another European study is conducted by Dimitropoulos and Asteriou (2010) who examine the impact of board independence on earnings management for 97 non-financial firms listed on the Athens Stock Exchange in Greece for the years 2000 through 2004. Consistent with Anglo-American countries' studies, they find that board independence is significantly and negatively related to earnings management.

Some recent Asian-based studies examine the effectiveness of board independence in constraining earnings management behaviour. Abdulrahman and Ali (2006) investigate this issue among 97 Malaysian listed firms over the period 2002-2003. Their study reveals that earnings management is positively related to the size of the board of directors but finds an insignificant relationship between either board independence or audit committee independence and earnings management. Siregar and Utama (2008) investigate the effect of ownership structure, firm size and Board of Directors practices on earnings management using Indonesian companies listed on the Jakarta Stock Exchange. They do not find evidence that firms with independent boards engage in informative earnings management. Their sample contains 144 firms and covered the periods 1995-1996 and 1999-2002. However, Jaggi *et al.* (2009) and Lo *et al.* (2010) investigate this association in Hong Kong and China respectively. Both document that independent boards provide effective monitoring of earnings management.

The obvious question that arises is why the results of some of these Asian-based studies conflict with Western results. A possible reason is that the first and second studies have relatively small samples, consisting of 97 firms and 144 firms respectively, while Jaggi *et al.* (2009) use a larger sample of 770 firm-year observations. Thus, sample size may have slightly affected the difference in the results of Jaggi *et al.* (2009) and the first two studies. Another possible explanation is that most Asian economies are largely dominated by family-controlled firms, where boards are more vulnerable to dominance by family members and this may contribute to weaken Board of Directors regimes and reduces independent directors' effectiveness. From an agency perspective, an independent board is more likely to be vigilant for agency problems as it includes a substantial number of non-executive directors (NEDs) who are dedicated to monitoring management's performance and behaviour (Fama, 1980). Fama (1980) asserts that boards which are dominated by insider directors are subject to self-monitoring problems and have weak monitoring of executive directors. Lawler *et al.* (2002) empirically supports the expectation that board independence enhances the monitoring function of the board.

H₁: There is a negative relationship between independent boards and earnings management.

2.2 Board Size

Klein (2002a) argue that board monitoring is positively associated with larger boards due to their ability to distribute the work load over a greater number of observers. The majority of the previous literature supports this argument, by finding that larger boards are strongly associated with lower levels of earnings management (Peasnell *et al.*, 2000a; Bedard *et al.*, 2004; Xie *et al.*, 2003; Yu, 2008). Xie *et al.* (2001) shows that earnings management is less likely to take place in firms with larger boards. Yu (2008) find that small boards seem more prone to failure to detect earnings management. One interpretation of this effect is that smaller boards may be more likely to be "captured" by management or dominated by blockholders, while larger boards are more capable of monitoring the actions of top management (Zahra and Pearce, 1989). On the other hand, Alonso *et al.* (2000) argue that large board exhibits poorer coordination and communication between members, and their results display a significant positive association between larger board size and earnings management. However, the findings of this study were inconsistent and should not be generalised due to several limitations. Firstly, the study covers only one year. Secondly, their study sample uses mixed data from ten different countries without controlling for different external factors, such as accounting standards and regulatory rules and, consequently, their study may be biased.

In Asia, Abdulrahman and Ali (2006) using Malaysian listed firms and Kao and Chen (2004) using Taiwanese firms, find that large board size is also related to a higher extent of earnings management. Considering the earlier discussion of the findings of Asian-based studies that board independence is less effective in constraining earnings management than in Anglo-American countries, and that large boards in some Asian studies show a positive association with earnings management, a further comment can be made. In less developed countries, boards may contain less effective independent directors because some may have been appointed through social connections rather than through ability and competition. In such boards, the advantages of size, namely, balance of power, the presence of more independent directors with valuable experience and diverse backgrounds, will be missing. Boards may be large in size but some outside directors may not be independent or effective which in turn will demolish the effect of board size on monitoring. From an agency perspective, larger boards are more likely to be vigilant for agency problems because substantial number of experienced directors can be deployed to monitor and review management actions.

The agency theory perspective also conceives that larger boards support effective monitoring by reducing CEO dominance within the board and, thus, they protect shareholders' interests (Singh & Harianto, 1989). Larger boards improve the bargaining position of the board with regard to the CEO and, thus, larger boards are more effective in monitoring the management. In addition, larger boards are likely to provide more independent directors, expertise and diversity and to delegate more responsibilities to board committees than smaller boards, hence increase the board's monitoring capacity in order to prevent or limit managerial opportunistic behaviour (Pearce and Zahra, 1992). Consequently, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H₂: There is a negative relationship between large board size and earnings management

2.3 Board Meetings

Directors on boards that meet frequently are more likely to discharge their duties in accordance with shareholders' interests because more time can be devoted to monitoring issues such as earnings management, conflicts of interest and monitoring management. Conversely, boards that rarely meet may have no time to find out about such complex issues and may perhaps have time only to rubber-stamp management plans. Though there is extensive prior research on the independence and size of boards of directors, there are few studies of the impact of board meeting frequency on earnings management. Xie *et al.* (2003) find that earnings management is significantly negatively related to the number of board meetings. In addition, Ebrahim (2007) uses a sample of manufacturing firms for years 1999 and 2000, find that discretionary accruals are much lower when independent audit committees are more active but they do not show any evidence that board activity mediates the relationship between earnings management and board independence. One essential measure of the effectiveness of a board is how often the board members meet to discuss the various issues facing a firm. Diligent boards enhance the level of oversight, resulting in improved financial reporting quality. Carcello, *et al.* (2002) finds that quality of audit work is associated with the number of board meetings.

Vafeas (1999) views board meetings as an essential resource in improving the effectiveness of the board and they use this to represent the intensity of board activity. Many other studies, for example, Lipton and Lorsch (1992), suggest that one of the major impediments to board effectiveness is the lack of time to carry out the board's responsibilities. They add that boards that meet frequently are more likely to discharge their duties diligently and in accordance with shareholders' interests. This makes management monitoring more effective, resulting in improved earnings quality.

H₃: The number of Board meetings is negatively associated with earnings management.

2.4 CEO Duality

The prior literature investigates the duality role of chairman and CEO. Duality occurs when the same person occupies both the CEO and chairman positions on the board. It is argued in the governance literature that the objectivity and quality of board oversight may suffer if the CEO also chairs the board. Centralisation of power in a company can result in the CEO being able to exercise excessive influence over the board by setting board agendas, managing meetings and controlling the flow of information to its members (Persons, 2006). However, this study does not investigate the duality role because firms in this study's sample exhibit very high compliance with the Board of Directors recommendation that the two roles should be separated. More than 90% of firms in this sample separate the positions of chairman and CEO; thus, any test would be statistically unreliable. This study applies different measures to capture the effect of chairman independence. The Nigerian Securities and Exchange Codes of Corporate Governance (2007) specifies the criteria for chairman independence and this study applies these criteria to each firm's chairman to determine his or her independence.

Since this study is not testing the effect of duality on earnings management, a brief discussion of previous studies is used to illustrate that the chairman influences the quality of reported earnings. Anderson *et al.* (2003) find that the separation between CEO and board chair positions appears to positively influence the information content of accounting earnings. On the other hand, most of the empirical studies found no association between CEO duality and earnings management, such as Peasnell *et al.*, (2000); Bedard *et al.* (2004); Xie *et al.* (2003) and Chang and Sun, (2009). However, no previous study has investigated the chairman's independence according to the independence criteria set out in the Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission Codes of Corporate Governance (2007). The hypotheses development section will look at these independence criteria and the method to be used for measuring this variable.

The chairman of the board has the power to control the agenda and board meetings and is likely to influence the market's perception of the extent of managerial monitoring and of the financial reporting process. From the agency theory perspective, the chairman should be independent of the company's affairs and this is a useful check on a CEO's over-ambitious plans (Blackburn, 1994). Thus, the presence of an independent chairman indicates that more control is likely to be exercised over management's activities and behaviour (Dechow *et al.*, 1996).

In the prior literature, the commonly used measure for chairman independence is whether or not the roles of the chairman and CEO are combined. However, the vast majority of the literature finds no association between CEO duality and earnings management (see, for instance, Dechow *et al.*, 1996; Peasnell *et al.*, 2000; Chen and Kao, 2004; Chtourou *et al.*, 2008 and Chang and Sun, 2009). Chang and Sun (2009) state that they did not find evidence indicating that CEO duality is associated with increased earnings management in either the pre- or post-SOX periods. Another shortcoming of duality as a measure of chairman independence is the high proportion of firms with/without duality in the previous studies; thus, they may not capture variance in the discretionary accruals. Thus, a better measure of the independence of chairmen is needed in order to measure whether they discharge their duties adequately. Therefore, this study uses the independent chairman criteria of the Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission (2007) to judge the chairman's independence. Some Nigerian firms separate the role of the chairman and CEO however, the chairman is still non independent, for example, the chairman is the founder of the firm, has large ownership or has family connections with one of the board members. In these cases the chairman is considered non independent.

H₄: There is a negative association between the chairman's independence and earnings management.

2.5 Audit Committee Independence

In the USA, Xie *et al.* (2001) examine the effect of some characteristics of the audit committee on constraining earnings management and find that audit committee independence is not significantly associated with reduced levels of earnings management, while Klein (2002b) find that the extent of discretionary accruals is more pronounced for firms with audit committees comprising of less than the majority of independent directors. Bedard *et al.* (2004) provide results obtained from logistic regression analyses suggest that aggressive earnings management is negatively related to fully independent audit committees. Chang and Sun (2009) find similar results for cross-listed Canadian firms after the introduction of Sarbanes-Oxley Act. In Australia, Benkel, *et al.* (2006) find that higher levels of audit committee independence are associated with reduced levels of earnings management. In the same institutional context, Davidson *et al.* (2005) findings support the view that independent audit committees are significantly associated with a lower likelihood of earnings management. Piot and Janin (2007) found similar results using French firms.

In Asia, Siregar and Utama (2008) using Indonesian companies listed on the Jakarta Stock Exchange and Abdul Rahman and Ali (2006) using Malaysian listed firms, reveals insignificant relationships between independent audit committees and earnings management. The independence of non-executive directors sitting on audit committees is seen as one of the crucial factors contributing towards the effectiveness of Board of Directors (Collier, 1993). Its importance is also highlighted by the Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission Codes of Corporate Governance (2007), which require that the audit committees should consist of at least three independent directors. Thus, in order to function effectively, audit committees must be independent of the management as this allows both the internal and external auditors to remain free of undue influences and interferences from corporate executives.

H₅: Audit committee independence is negatively associated with earnings management.

2.6 Nomination and Remuneration Committee

Only two studies investigate the effect of either nomination or remuneration committee on earnings management. The first study is by Klein (2002), she tested if earnings management is positively related to the CEO's membership of nomination committee using data from 1991 to 1993 for a sample of USA firms and finds no association exist. However, she also finds a positive relation between the presence of the CEO in the remuneration committee and earnings management. The second study is conducted by Osma and Noguera (2007) and tests whether the existence of board monitoring committees constrains earnings manipulation for a Spanish sample of quoted companies during the period 1999-2001. They find that the independent nomination committee has a positive significant relationship with earnings management, contradicting agency theory predictions.

However, they find that the significant positive relationship between board independence and earnings management is moderated by nomination committee independence. Companies need to be objective in the nomination process for directors. The board needs to have a balanced portfolio of members with diverse backgrounds and specialisations. From an agency theory perspective, nomination committees can play a vital role in enhancing the independence of the board and reducing the influence of management (Jensen, 1993). Having a nomination committee will effectively delegate the director selection process to a group rather than a single person (usually the chairman of the board or the CEO), which is independent of the management and which can make independent recommendations.

One important aspect of the remuneration committee is that, if it discharges its roles adequately, it safeguards board independence by preventing independent directors from receiving any remuneration other than their fees as directors; this is an important code condition for their independence. In addition, the remuneration committee has a key role to play in ensuring a fair and appropriate remuneration scheme. This, in turn, ensures that management ownership is designed to align the interests of shareholders and management, which will work towards constraining management opportunistic behaviour such as earnings management.

H₆: The existence of Remuneration & Nomination committee is negatively associated with earnings management.

3. Methodology

This study covers ten years of reporting periods from December 2012 to December 2021. There are several reasons for this choice. Firstly, this study uses the Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission Codes of Corporate Governance (2007) as a guide for Board of Directors and other top management staff. Secondly, due to the large amount of data that has to be hand-collected for the Board of Directors variables, limiting the study period to ten years makes that task viable.

Table 1
Sample size and selection procedures for the study period

Description	2012-2021
Initial sample (all Nigerian listed firms)	112
<u>Excluded:</u>	(37)
Banks and insurance companies	
Final sample	75

The initial sample for this study is all Nigerian listed companies, which are required to comply with Board of Directors mechanisms recommended by NSEC. Financial firms (banks and insurance firms) are then excluded from the initial sample because their special accounting practices means that the discretionary accruals model does not apply to them, as illustrated in previous empirical studies (e.g. Peasnell *et al.*, 2000; Chtourou *et al.*, 2008). note that there is no missing cell for all Board of Directors variables mainly due to the strict requirements by the NGX. The usable sample is 750 firm year observations. The companies are normally distributed from an industry perspective. The Building & Construction, Agriculture & Food and Industrial Investment industries, collectively account for around one third of the sample. The other eleven industries each represent from 3% to 11% of the total sample. Data on earnings management, Board of Directors and control variables are hand collected from the 2012-2021 annual reports for each firm (source: NGX). The process involves an examination of the directors' profiles and the Board of Directors report to identify the independence and the activity of the board subcommittees and their members.

The most widely used method to measure earnings management in the literature are the Jones (1991) and the modified Jones (Dechow *et al.*, 1995) models. However, Kothari *et al.* (2005) argue that measuring earnings management without controlling for firm performance will produce misspecification in the earnings management model. Therefore, recent studies such as Chang and Sun (2009), Jaggi *et al.* (2009) and Sun *et al.* (2010) favour a performance-matched accrual measure proposed by Kothari *et al.* (2005), which includes (lagged) return on assets in order to diminish the problems of heteroscedasticity and misspecification issues arising with prior models. Other models include De Angelo Score, Yoon, Kim and Woodruff Discretionary Accrual Score, Beneish Fraud M Score.

In the first step, total accruals ($TACC_{jt}$) of firm j in the year t are calculated as the difference between operating earnings ($EARN_{jt}$) and net cash flow from operations (CFO_{jt}):

$$TACC_{jt} = EARN_{jt} - CFO_{jt} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Next, the industry sectors' estimate for all firms within the same industry is computed separately for each year. Using the modified Jones model as per Kothari *et al.* (2005), total accruals are scaled by lagged total assets (TA_{jt-1}) and regressed against its components including an intercept as follows:

$$\frac{TACC_{jt}}{TA_{jt-1}} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \left(\frac{1}{TA_{jt-1}} \right) + \alpha_2 \left(\frac{\Delta SALE_{jt} - \Delta REC_{jt}}{TA_{jt-1}} \right) + \alpha_3 \left(\frac{PPE_{jt}}{TA_{jt-1}} \right) + \alpha_4 ROA_{jt-1} + \varepsilon_{jt} \quad (2)$$

Whereas:

$TACC_{jt}$	= total accruals for firm j in the year t
TA_{jt-1}	= total assets for firm j at end in the year $t - 1$
$\Delta SALE_{jt}$	= change in sales for firm j in year t from year $t - 1$
ΔREC_{jt}	= change in accounts receivables for firm j in year t from year $t - 1$
PPE_{jt}	= property, plant and equipment for firm j at the end of year t
ROA_{jt-1}	= return on assets for firm j at end of the year $t - 1$
ε_{jt}	(net income divided by lagged total assets) = residuals

The change in sales in equation 2 has been adjusted by the change of accounts receivables as managers may boost earnings in the current period by an early recognition of revenues. Hence, without having taken this into account, the change in sales would lead to an endogenous bias (Jeter & Shivakumar, 1999). Therefore, Dechow *et al.* (1995) suggests that an adjustment by change in accounts receivables would overcome this bias, which was later adopted by Kothari *et al.* (2005). Using the estimated coefficients a_0 , a_1 , a_2 , a_3 and a_4 for each industry obtained from equation 2, the firms' non-discretionary accruals ($NDACC_{jt}$) are calculated:

$$NDACC_{jt} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \left(\frac{1}{TA_{jt-1}} \right) + \alpha_2 \left(\frac{\Delta SALE_{jt} - \Delta REC_{jt}}{TA_{jt-1}} \right) + \alpha_3 \left(\frac{PPE_{jt}}{TA_{jt-1}} \right) + \alpha_4 ROA_{jt-1}$$

equation (3)

Finally, firms' discretionary accruals are obtained by subtracting non-discretionary accruals (equation 3) from total accruals (equation 2):

$$DACC_{jt} = TACC_{jt} - NDACC_{jt} \quad \text{equation (4)}$$

$$ADACC_{jt} = |DACC_{jt}| \quad \text{equation (5)}$$

Following previous research, the magnitude of absolute discretionary accruals ($ADACC$) is used as proxy for earnings management as managers have incentives to engage in either income-increasing or income-decreasing earnings management.

Table 2 summarises the explanatory variables, providing brief definitions and indicating the predicted association.

Table 2
Summary of variables and their measurements

Symbol	Variable	Operationalisation
DACC	Earnings management	Absolute value of the discretionary accruals estimated by the Kothari et al. (2005) model used by Yahaya et al. (2017), Ibrahim et al. (2019), Yahaya (2022), Yahaya & Abdulfatah (2022)
BIND	Board independence	A dummy variable that takes the value of one if the proportion of independent non-executive directors to total board members is above sample median, and zero otherwise (Aliyu et al., 2021; Yahaya, 2022; Yahaya et al., 2022).
BSIZE	Board size	The number of directors on the board (Ajibulu et al., 2021; Jegede et al., 2018; Kolawole et al., 2020; Yahaya & Tijani, 2020; Yahaya & Apochi, 2021; Yahaya, 2022; Yahaya & Apochi, 2022; Yahaya & Mohammed, 2022)
BMEET	Board meetings	The number of board meetings held annually by the board of directors (Abu et al., 2019; Andrew et al., 2018; Tijjani & Yahaya, 2022)
CHAIRIND	Chairman independence	A dummy variable that takes the value of one if the chairman is independent according to the independence criteria recommended by the NSEC, and zero otherwise.
AUDIND	Audit committee independence	A dummy variable that takes the value of one if the audit committee is composed entirely of independent directors, and zero otherwise.
R&NIND	Remuneration & Nomination committee independence	A dummy variable that takes the value of one if the nomination & remuneration committee exists, and zero otherwise.

Previous studies have indicated that certain other factors can influence the magnitude of earnings management. Therefore, the following control variables, which have been found in relevant studies: managerial ownership, institutional ownership, firm size, leverage, cash flow from operations, return on assets and audit firm size.

Table 3
Summary of control variables and their measurements

Variable	Definition	Sources
Firm Size	Natural logarithm of firmsize (measured by total assets)	e.g. Xie et al. (2003), Piot and Janin (2006), Habbash et al. (2010), Sun et al. (2010) and Dimitropoulos and Asteriou (2010), Yahaya (2006), Yahaya & Tijjani (2021)
Firm Leverage	Leverage (measured by long-term debt to lagged total assets)	e.g. Chang and Sun (2009) and Dimitropoulos and Asteriou (2010), Onwe et al. (2020), Yahaya et al. (2019), Yahaya & Tijjani (2021)
Cash flow from Operations	Cash flow from operations deflated by total assets	e.g. Bédard et al. (2004), Piot and Janin (2006), Abdul Rahman and Ali <i>et al.</i> (2006).
Firm Performance	Return on assets	e.g. Bédard et al. (2004), Abdul Rahman and Ali <i>et al.</i> (2006), Habbash et al. (2010), Sun et al. (2010)
Audit Quality	Whether the company is audit by one of the Big4 audit firms.	e.g. Abdul Rahman and Ali <i>et al.</i> (2006) and Baxter and Cotter (2009)
Managerial Ownership	The percentage of total shares held by executive directors divided by the total number of shares.	e.g. Warfield, et al. (1995) and Larcker and Richardson (2004)
Institutional Ownership	owned by institutional investors divided by the total number of shares.	e.g. Larcker and Richardson (2004) and Peasnell <i>et al.</i> (2005).

This study uses the following panel data fixed-effects ordinary least square (OLS) regression analysis to test the association between the dependent variable of earnings management and the independent variables of Board of Directors.

$$DACC_{i,t} = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 BIND_{i,t} + \gamma_2 BSIZE_{i,t} + \gamma_3 BMEET_{i,t} + \gamma_4 CHAIRIND_{i,t} + \gamma_5 R\&NE_{i,t} + \gamma_6 MANGOWN_{i,t} + \gamma_7 INSTOWN_{i,t} + \gamma_8 SIZE_{i,t} + \gamma_9 LEV_{i,t} + \gamma_{10} CFO_{i,t} + \gamma_{11} BIG4_{i,t} + \gamma_{12} ROA_{i,t} + e_{i,t}$$

Absolute value of the discretionary accruals estimated by the Kothari *et al.* (2005) model.

A dummy variable that takes the value of one if the proportion of independent non-executive directors to total board members is above sample median, and zero otherwise.

BSIZE is the number of directors in the board.

BMEET is the number of board meetings held annually by the board of directors.

A dummy variable that takes the value of one if the chairman is independent according to the independence criteria recommended by the NSEC, and zero otherwise.

A dummy variable that takes the value of one if the audit committee is composed entirely of independent directors, and zero otherwise.

A dummy variable that takes the value of one if the nomination & remuneration committee exists, and zero otherwise.

The percentage of total shares held by executive directors divided by the total number of shares.

The percentage of shares owned by institutional investors divided by the total number of shares.

LEV is leverage = Total long-term debt divided by total assets.

SIZE is firm size = the natural logarithm of total assets at year-end.

Cash flows from operating activities divided by beginning of period total assets.

ROA is Net income divided by the total assets at the beginning of the year.

A dummy variable that takes the value of one if a firm is audit by one of the Big4 audit firms, and zero otherwise.

4. Results and Discussion

The descriptive statistics of all variables is presented in Table 4. The absolute value of discretionary accruals for the companies in this study's sample has a small mean value of 0.08, whereas the minimum value is much closer to 0 (0.0001). These findings are consistent with Klein (2002) who obtains a minimum value of absolute DACC among large US firms of 0.00002. However, the mean of absolute DACC among US companies in Klein (2002) and Xie *et al.* (2003) studies are similar at 0.07 and 0.10 respectively.

Table 4
Pooled Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Median	Std. Dev	Minimum	Maximum
DACC	0.082	0.053	0.102	0.000	0.892
BSIZE	8.213	8.000	1.730	4.000	12.00
BMEET	4.533	4.000	1.826	0.000	9.000
BIND	0.669	1.000	0.471	0.000	1.000
CHAIRND	0.766	1.000	0.424	0.000	1.000
ACIND	0.899	1.000	0.301	0.000	1.000
RNEXIST	0.870	1.000	0.337	0.000	1.000
MANGOWN	0.179	0.079	0.211	0.000	0.890
INSTOWN	0.143	0.000	0.198	0.000	0.750
BIG4	0.608	1.000	0.489	0.000	1.000
LEVG	0.087	0.019	0.138	0.000	0.596
CFO	0.086	0.067	0.105	-0.199	0.361
ROA	0.069	0.058	0.087	-0.137	0.299
SIZE	9.239	9.186	0.709	7.869	11.473

This study sample shows high percentages of independence in boards of directors. However, 90% of the sample firms have fully independent audit committee rather than the 100% independence level recommended by the NSEC. When the chairman independence criteria are applied, around 76% of the chairmen can be considered to be independent. About 13% of the sample firms do not have remuneration and nomination committee. The average board size in this study is about 8 members (mean = 8.21). Board size in the Nigerian listed firms appear to be similar to Malaysian listed firms documented by Abdulrahman and Ali *et al.* (2006) and firms in Hong Kong in Jaggi *et al.* (2009),

Table 5
Correlations Coefficients

	DACC	BSZE	BMEET	BIND	CHAIRND	ACIND	RNEXIST	MANGOWN	INSTOWN	BIG4	LEVG	ROA	CFO	size
DACC	1													
BSZE	-0.1249*	1												
BMEET	0.0342	0.1509*	1											
BIND	-0.1041	0.1559*	0.2573*	1										
CHAIRND	-0.0169	-0.1545*	0.0118	0.2944*	1									
ACIND	-0.0295	-0.0726	0.1516*	0.078	0.2337*	1								
RNEXIST	-0.1267*	0.0579	-0.0992	-0.0108	-0.0682	0.1045	1							
MANGOWN	-0.0615	-0.0184	-0.0298	-0.0886	-0.1635*	-0.081	0.1526*	1						
INSTOWN	-0.0312	0.0195	-0.0948	-0.1065	-0.0749	-0.0329	0.0831	0.1340*	1					
BIG4	0.0068	0.2080*	0.1389*	0.1406*	-0.0155	0.0326	0.0124	0.1707*	0.2478*	1				
LEVG	-0.015	0.0397	0.0659	0.1155*	0.0765	0.083	-0.0018	-0.035	0.2100*	0.2351*	1			
ROA	-0.0438	0.0602	0.0887	0.0844	-0.1119*	-0.0273	0.1887*	0.2234*	0.054	0.0784	-0.125*	1		
CFO	0.0855	0.0147	0.0551	0.0255	-0.1100*	-0.0703	0.0956	0.1324*	0.0147	0.0099	-0.0672	0.643*	1	
SIZE	0.0671	0.3534*	0.3095*	0.2597*	0.0526	0.0419	-0.1061	-0.0577	0.1871*	0.3975*	0.4927*	0.0038	0.0587	1

both report a mean board size of around 8 members, smaller than board size in US firms (e.g., mean size of about 12 in Xie *et al.*, 2003). Surprisingly, number of board meetings is significantly lower than both US and UK firms. 4.5 meetings in Nigerian listed firms comparing to about 8 meeting in both USA and the UK, see Xie *et al.* (2003) and Habbash *et al.* (2010) studies.

From the correlation coefficients analysis, shown in Table 5, no high correlation is found among the variables. As a result, collinearity does not appear to create a threat to the interpretation of regression coefficients of in this model. However, the highest coefficient is 0.64 between cash from operations (CFO) and return on assets (ROA) This correlation is expected and is found in previous studies, such as that of Abdulrahman and Ali *et al.* (2006) who report even higher collinearity between these two variables (67%) but considered this collinearity to be harmless. Another significant and relatively high correlation is between firm size (SIZE) and board size (BSIZE), suggesting that large firms have large boards. Better performed firms have a positive correlation with managerial ownership. All these variables are included in the same model since the correlations are not strong (lower than 0.800). Gujarati (2003) recommend 0.80 as the threshold at which multicollinearity concerns may threaten the regression analysis. Further, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) tests were carried out and no harmful correlation were reported (results reported in the index). Gujarati (2003) suggests that a VIF value of less than 10 is acceptable; the maximum VIF value is 2.05.

Table 6 reports the regression of discretionary accruals on Board of Directors. The adjusted R^2 obtained for this model is fairly comparable with those in similar studies, for example, those of Jaggi *et al.* (2009) with adj R^2 of 6%, Dimitropoulos and Asteriou (2010) and Baxter and Cotter (2009) with adj R^2 of 9%. Consistent with the first hypothesis, the result indicates that there is a negative and significant relationship (coefficient = -.025 and $p < .05$) between board independence and the indicator of earnings management. This finding is in line with the previous findings of Klein (2002b), Xie *et al.* (2003), Peasnell *et al.* (2005), Benkel *et al.* (2006), Dimitropoulos and Asteriou (2010) and Lo, *et al.* (2010). In terms of the second hypothesis, this study finds that board size (BRDSIZE) is significantly and negatively associated with earnings management. The result indicates that larger boards are more effective in monitoring financial reporting.

The negative association between large boards and the empirical indicator of earnings management is similar to the findings of Peasnell *et al.* (2005), Chtourou *et al.* (2001), Xie *et al.* (2003) and Yu (2008). They find that board size is strongly and negatively associated with lower levels of earnings management. This study's result also supports the findings of Zahra and Pearce (1989) that larger boards are more capable than smaller boards of monitoring the actions of management. Inconsistent with this study's third expectation, the coefficients of (BMEET) are insignificant. In fact, this result suggests that directors now have a busier schedule of bureaucratic meetings that makes them less responsive to essential challenges and, indeed, less attentive to monitoring needs. This result supports the argument of Lipton and Lorsch (1992), who point out that board meetings are not necessarily functional because, given their limited time; they restrict the meaningful exchange of ideas among directors or with managers.

Taking the result of the variable (BSIZE) into consideration, along with the result of the ineffective impact of (BMEET), the non-binding of board meetings can have a joint interpretation. These results suggest that if the board size is large, board meetings may not be the best means of communication between directors. As the board size increases, there are more people to share the responsibilities but communication is less effective. Thereby, more board meetings may be more fruitful only for small-sized boards. Given that the board size is generally large in this study sample, as shown in the descriptive analysis, board meetings may not be very effective in monitoring management activities.

Table 6
Regression Results

DACC	Expected Sign	Coefficient	t-statistic
BRDINDP	-	-0.027	-2.030**
BRDSIZE	-	-0.010	-2.760***
BRDMEET	-	0.002	0.630
CHAIRIND	-	-0.003	-0.210
RNEXIST	-	-0.022	-1.270
ACINDEP	-	-0.010	-0.520
MANGOWN	?	-0.026	-0.940
INSTOWN	?	-0.021	-0.700
BIG4	?	0.008	0.600
LEVG	?	-0.061	-1.260
ROA	?	-0.154	-1.760*
CFO	?	0.168	2.420***
SIZE	?	0.023	2.090**
cons	?	-0.006	-0.060
Adj R ²		8%	
F(13,318)		2.26 ***	

The result of hypotheses 4, 5 and 6 reveal insignificant but as expected negatively signed coefficients which do not support these hypotheses. Even though board sub-committees, namely the remuneration & nomination and audit committees have been introduced and emphasised as essential parts of the governance required by recent Board of Directors regulations in Nigeria, it seems that these committees have not yet achieved the expected efficiency that enables them to discharge their monitoring duties adequately. The non finding results of ownership structures variables are consistent with the previous UK evidence of Peasnell *et al.* (2005). This may raise questions about the role and the characteristics of Nigerian institutional investors and managerial holdings and their awareness of, and reaction to, management discretion. CFO, ROA and SIZE are statistically significant, while other control variables do not exhibit any statistically significant results. These results suggest that large firms have more pressure on their management to report more predictable earnings. Thus, managers are likely to engage in earnings management to achieve this predictability which consists with prior studies' findings such as Dimitropoulos and Asteriou (2010) and with expectations of agency theory.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper reports empirical evidence of the effectiveness of Board of Directors as a structure of corporate governance as guided by NSEC in 2007 on limiting earnings management practice in Nigerian listed firms over the period of ten years from 2012 to 2021. In general, these findings suggest that firms with effective Board of Directors mechanisms undertake less accruals management. Particularly, independent and large boards are effective in constraining earnings management practices. Overall, although not all Board of Directors variables support the stated hypotheses; this study has achieved its objective by identifying the attributes that answer the research question. This study, therefore, finds that the agency theory offers some explanation of the association between Board of Directors and earnings management practice. Like most studies of a similar nature, this study is subject to a number of limitations. First, even though this study uses an accurate and recent proxy for earnings management, and although discretionary accruals is the standard measure of earnings management, this measure is prone to measurement errors and thus the validity of these findings depends upon the accuracy of discretionary accruals as an appropriate proxy for earnings management. Secondly, the study sample consists of large publicly traded Nigerian firms and it is uncertain that the findings could be generalised to smaller firms.

Despite these inherent limitations, the findings provide useful insights to regulators, especially NSEC, for improving the current regulations on Board of Directors mechanisms. There are several recommendations that can be drawn from this study results. First, board sub-committees namely the remuneration & nomination and audit committees need to be improved in order to achieve the expected efficiency that enables them to discharge their monitoring duties adequately. The remuneration & nomination committee for example need to be separated. The nomination committee's role should be restricted to monitoring board composition, developing the selection criteria, assessing board members' competencies, reviewing succession, evaluating the board's performance, and recommending the appointment and removal of directors. Whereas, the remuneration committee's responsibility is to set a compensation package that protects the interest of the shareholders. Thus, the remuneration committee guarantees the competence of independent board members and acts as one of the monitors of the CEO. Having all of these responsibilities in one committee creates too much power for joint committee members, which may create another information asymmetry problem.

Second, the current situation of chairmen independence needs to be re-considered. Although chairman and CEO positions are separated, chairmen still have some undesirable relationships and interests in the company which may deter their independence. Stricter and clearer regulations should be introduced here to safeguard chairmen independence. Finally, emphasis of the relationship between shareholders and institutional investors is required, as the impact of institutional shareholders monitoring effect seems lacking. This is one of the fundamental Board of Directors attributes that recent Board of Directors codes updates have been working on, see for example the update of UK Board of Directors Code (2010). The result also improves investors' awareness of the extent of Board of Directors effectiveness in improving the earning quality. Last, but not least, the findings of this study add to the Board of Directors and earnings quality literature on less developed economies. This study's findings may be generalised to other emerging countries of institutional environments similar to that of Nigeria.

In addition to the recommendations mentioned above, there are some possible extensions to this study, earnings management is only one way to examine the financial reporting system integrity, thus, it may be appealing to examine the effectiveness of Board of Directors using other related earnings quality measurements (e.g. fraud, restatements, earnings informativeness etc.). It may be beneficial to expand this study for 14 years in order to investigate the impact of Board of Directors enforcement immediately after 2007 by comparing two sub-periods prior and post enforcement date. Finally, we would stress that too short a time has passed to reach a definitive conclusion. The Board of Directors is a new monitoring mechanism imported from the Anglo-Saxon countries, and Nigeria has not yet developed a Board of Directors culture. Further research in this area in the future will be very useful.

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